

Psychological Resilience: An Exploratory Analysis of Teenage Pregnancy Phenomenon in Bacoor City, Cavite

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Abstract

Teenage pregnancy has been a worldwide issue that raised many campaigns and awareness to lessen its occurrence. As stated by National Demographic and Health Survey in 2023, one out of every young Filipino woman aged 15 to 19 is already a mother with their first child. Commission on Population (2023) shows that CALABARZON tops the list with the highest teenage pregnancy rate; this includes Laguna, Cavite, and Batangas. Bacoor, Cavite has the second-highest number of live births, with a percentage of 14.82 (Philippine Statistic Authority, 2022). Therefore, in partnership with the different non-government agencies, the government should exert efforts to resolve this issue. Teenage Pregnancies are often associated with social development issues such as lack of sufficient sex education, reproductive health programs, and educational facilities. These circumstances opted for the lack of awareness and knowledge of the said issue, catalyzing conditions that render high numbers of adolescents engaged in teenage pregnancy. Hence, it conveys a social stigma in various countries and cultures. This study focused on exploring the lived experiences of Filipino teenage mothers, specifically from Bacoor, Cavite, about their psychological resilience. Delving into their personal experiences before, during, and after they prepare for accepting their new roles as mothers.

Keywords: Psychological Resilience, Teenage Pregnancy, Phenomenological Study.

Introduction

Teenage life is a stage where adolescents are enjoying and living their life to the fullest. It is a phase wherein physical, psychological, and social values change for a teenager. However, teenage life does not only accompany happy events it is also a turning point where adversities emerge. This sometimes includes family problems, educational pressure, substance abuse, relationship conflicts, and sexual involvement.

In the past years, teenage pregnancy is one of the common problems of adolescents (Levy, 2020). According to the World Health Organization (2020), it has become a global problem as it continues rising each year. This global problem does not only occur in low-income countries but also in the middle- and high-income countries. In 2019, the Philippines ranked second to the highest in Southeast Asia by having 5.9% of girls that have been pregnant in their teenage years. The country has been labeled teenage pregnancy as a "National Social Emergency" (Save the Children, 2023).

When teens become mothers, their life transitions are shortened, and their life options are restricted in many ways. At a very young age, they have to carry big responsibilities which do not give them a choice but to take an adult's job to survive and fill in their duties as parents.

They face challenges that affect their physical, emotional and mental health. According to the World Health Organization (2012), young mothers face many issues including dropping out of school, lack of sources of income, and family support. While these issues and problems are affecting both the mothers and children, many young mothers work hard and persevere which shows their psychological resilience in times of adversities.

In the study of Rosario et.al (2016), being a teenage mother still has positive attributes in terms of the development in their different aspects, instances where people thought that teen mothers were more determined, and goal-oriented as a result of the intervention. Moreover, motherhood made a way for teen mothers to alter and redirect their lives, concentrating on their future as well as the future of their child or children.

Over the past years, most of the studies about teenage pregnancy have focused on its effects and factors affecting teenage mothers. The concept of psychological resilience is a new way to address and explore the life experiences of young mothers. As to how they cope up and overcome adversities along their journey in their pregnancy and being a mother.

The purpose of this study is to explore the psychological resilience and understand the lived experiences of teenage mothers ages 15-19 (Philippine Statistic Authority, 2022) in Bacoor, Cavite. As of the data gathered by Commission on Population (2018), CALABARZON tops the list with the highest teenage pregnancy rate in the country; the top 3s are Laguna, Cavite, and Batangas. Bacoor, Cavite has the second-highest number of live births followed with 14.82 percent (Philippine Statistic Authority, 2022). More importantly, this study will be beneficial to the participants in raising awareness towards the issue of the teenage pregnancy phenomenon. This will also help the locale of the study to develop more programs intended for providing support for teenage

mothers and their children. This will serve as a platform to assist by presenting the lists of programs offered by the government which are basically for teenage mothers.

Methodology

Research Design

The study will utilize qualitative phenomenological research exploring the psychological resilience of teenage pregnancy in Bacoor Cavite. The instrument is a semistructured type of interview guide questionnaire that was developed by the investigators aiming towards the objectives of the study. The components of 18-item guide questions were validated by subject-matter experts to ensure consistency and sensitivity on each item.

Teenage pregnancy is a global phenomenon that must be addressed to alleviate the problems of maternal adolescent childbearing, especially in third-world countries.

In addition, Salvador (2016) states that phenomenology is the study of the phenomenon, indicating that each situation or experience can only be experienced by a single person who has gained new perceptions and insights. Moreover, a phenomenological inquiry is focused on exploring and interpreting human lived experiences. This can be accomplished by determining the nature of the experiences and the essences of human lived experiences.

Furthermore, this phenomenological study was based on Sister Callista Roy's (1980) – Adaptation Theory. This theory *'defines adaptation as the process by which an individual or group makes conscious choices to cope with his or her situation. Adaptive responses increase people's ability to cope and to achieve their goals including survival, growth, mastery of their lives, and personal and environmental transformation'*. Fortunately, according to Roy's adaptation theory, there are four distinct modes: physiologic (basic needs such as food, sleep, air, water, and the needs for body protection); self-concept (beliefs and feelings about oneself); role identity/function (personal viewpoint on the social world); and interdependence (personal relationship with the entire organization).

As a result, an individual is an open adaptive system that responds to stressors using coping skills. Thus, the 'person' represents teenage mothers. In addition, according to Roy, an environment should include "all situations, circumstances, and factors that surround and influence the person's development and behavior." The participants' struggles in dealing with pregnancy and motherhood can be summed up by the environment. Thus, Roy aims to "promote adaptation in each of the four modes, which could contribute to the person's wellbeing, quality of life, and dignity in dying."

Participants of the Study

Purposive sampling was used to reach the target participants as it allows the researchers to interview those who had experienced teenage pregnancy who possess the following qualifications:

- Filipino citizen;
- Had experienced teenage pregnancy or early motherhood; and
- Have at least 1-2 years old children.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers utilized books, articles, journals, and interviews as reliable resources in gathering the data needed for the study. To gather the data from the participants, the following steps will be done by the researchers:

Step 1. The researchers conducted interviews prior to the guide questions construction. A semi-structured interview was facilitated. Thus, observations, use of field notes (personal, transcript, and analytical), audio-visual recordings, and qualitative documents was used to supplement the data collection process. Informed consent was also provided to secure confidentiality.

Step 2. The guide questions underwent a validation process by the subject-matter experts composed of licensed psychologists, psychometricians, social workers, and professional teachers which made the set of items in the interview guide question more reliable and consistent.

Step 3. The researchers submitted their manuscript to the Ethical Review Board to allow them to conduct their study.

Step 4. The researchers submitted a request letter to the campus administrator of Cavite State University-Bacoor City Campus to allow them to conduct the study outside the campus.

Step 5. Researchers sent out invitations to potential voluntary participants through formal notice via online platforms.

Step 6. Researchers discussed the rights of the participants from the moment they agreed to be part of the study. This included the rights to proceed or withdraw anytime to preserve the principle of autonomy and confidentiality.

Step 7. Upon signing the informed consent, the researchers will build a rapport towards the selected participants through the use of Filipino Research Methods such as "*Pakikipagpalagayang-loob*", "*Pakikipagkuwentuhan*", and "*Pakikiramdam*".

Step 8. The investigators conducted the study through validated interview guide questions. Thus, immoral or triggering statements were eliminated for the protection of the participants' well-being. All the operations will be done through online platforms.

Step 9. After interviewing the participants, the investigators conducted a debriefing session to ensure that the research study did not tap any sensitive issues in order to give assurance on each participant in case any possible issue arises.

Step 10. The gathered data from the participants was analyzed, transcribed, formulated into meanings, categorized, and clustered into themes, and will be validated to ensure consistent narrative results. This investigation utilized the thematic approach for qualitative content analysis by phenomenological data analysis of Colaizzi.

Data Analysis

For the preparation of data analysis, interviews were transcribed verbatim. To maintain confidentiality, coding methods and pseudonyms were used. To explain the nature of the phenomenon, qualitative content analysis inspired by Colaizzi (1978) will be used under the intended methodology.

Figure 2. Summary of Colaizzi's Strategy for Phenomenological Data Analysis (Morrow et.al., 2015)

In figure 2, each of the transcripts will undergo read and re-read to acquire the general information of the topic. Then, for each transcript, significant statements concerning the phenomenon under study should be extracted. These statements must be recorded on a separate sheet noting their pages and line numbers. Meanings should be formulated from these significant statements. The formulated meanings should be sorted into categories, clusters of themes, and themes. The findings of the study should be integrated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study. The fundamental structure of the phenomenon should be described. Finally, validation of the findings should be sought from the research participants to compare the researcher's descriptive results with their experiences.

Ethical Consideration

This research study adhered to its ethical guidelines. Thus, the researchers had to deal with ethical challenges throughout the study, from the conceptualization to the execution of the study; The researchers discussed and provided online consent forms for the respondents with the description and nature of the study indicated on it. Subsequently, the investigators assured that the respondents gathered data would be treated with the utmost confidentiality and that their identity will not be disclosed to anyone as it is exclusive to the researchers' team only. The researchers also undergo a validation process which eliminates triggering questions relating to the study in order to protect the participants' well-being. Moreover, the investigators delivered interview questions with the use of appropriate language and with professional care in the manner of questioning the participants to reduce minimal risks. Thus, with regards to the interview process, it was necessary to conduct a debriefing to the participants beforehand. Also in mind, the whole process of interview was strictly adhered to and acknowledged the choice of each participant by not forcing them to answer questions if they choose not to disclose to.

Prior to the interview process, eligibility criteria, the study's intent, the advantages, and disadvantages of taking part in the study, the costs and benefits of participating in the study, compensation, how confidentiality will be protected, their right to skip questions or leave the interview at any time, and contact details were all included in the informed consent. Most of all, the data collected from the participants will be recorded and encoded to a software that features data analysis and will be saved and protected in a high-security laptop computer then all data files should be stored securely in a safe or locked file cabinet. Only the investigators have access to these files and data. The research will only be operated via online transactions throughout the process as in accordance with the new normal academic system and pandemic protocols.

Results and Interpretation

Thematic analysis of the responses was done based on the interviews. This matches the qualitative in-depth interviewing since the research subscribed to openended questions and also probed on the initial answers of participants. The themes to be discussed are: (1.) experiences with family, partner, community, and school; and coping mechanisms. (2) perceptions and feelings towards teenage pregnancy, (3) meaningful goals, (4) barriers on achieving dreams and hope, (5) sources of social support.

(1) Experiences with family, partner, community, and school; and coping mechanisms.

Teenage mothers presumably are individuals who had unfinished dreams and hopes for their future together with the responsibilities they shoulder. Some of them are unsure where they can get help to meet the needs of their children. For some, they considered themselves fortunate to have parents, partners, and community programs that helped them survive the crisis because they were unable to support themselves financially. The individuals in question provided medical services as well as basic necessities such as milk, vitamins, and diapers. However, there are social struggles that influence and deter their drives to continue pursuing those dreams and passions they had. The support they feel and receive from their environments or the people that surround them is greatly influential to boost or lose their motivation towards their goals.

Father of the child

Having a child is a lifetime responsibility that is equivalent to giving what the child needs. These can be made by expressing a full-time attention to the child and having stable financial income. In most cases, a mother and father should work together to fulfill these needs for their child. But when a father fails to take full responsibility, the mother alone will be the one to carry the responsibility as parent. This might attempt to guide the mother to establish psychological resilience or might hinder her to develop it.

Personal experiences before and after the labor

When a woman becomes a mother, her overall experience before and after her pregnancy journey can embark memories that she is not able to easily forget. These experiences can be seen as an indicator of motivation to develop psychological resilience or can be a downfall if mothers distinguish it as a terrifying thought throughout her life. Majority of the participants' were molded and strengthened by their personal experiences as teenage mothers which obviously influenced their resilience psychologically and to some extent or aspect of their life.

Self-care provisions as a young mother for her child

Mothers are known as the best in taking care of their children. These young mothers have different ways to not just take care of their baby but also themselves.

Challenging Aspects as Teenage Mother

If mothers who had their child in their adult years faced challenges, teenage mothers experienced it also. The sudden shifting of responsibilities made the young mothers face conflicts in time management and to their psychological being. However, there are also young mothers who learned to not be affected by their situation.

Positive Aspects as a Teenage Mother.

When there are challenges as a young mother, there might be a positive aspect that the young mothers hold on to overcome the depth of responsibilities. The experiences of participants led them to find some positive aspects and these are accountability, their children, being physically able and parental awareness.

Reinforcements since pregnancy

These young mothers could not do it on their own without the help and support from their loved ones. They have these bigger responsibilities which in need of helping hands or reinforcements coming from the people that surround them. Also, they had a variety of ways on how to handle personal problems along the way.

Affected aspect of being a young mother in terms of:***Physically***

Indeed, it is not an easy road for parents especially for these young mothers to sustain their self-composure while managing their own family relationship. Undeniably, there will always be aspects of their lives that could be affected as young mothers such as; physically, emotionally, mentally, and spiritually. That said, they have struggled with their physical aspect which is also inevitable to experience by future parents.

Emotionally

One aspect of the life of these young mothers that really affects them the most coming from their individual experiences is their emotional struggles before, during, and up until the present situation they are in. On the other hand, it made them realize how vulnerable and strong they are as they overcome those difficult moments.

Mentally

It reflected that these young mothers are not just strong physically but also their situation contributed to their courageous mental attitude. It is really essential to have a powerful mindset especially when trials come along the way. It is their tool to overcome hardships and struggles just to sustain their established teenage family relationship.

Spiritually

Having a firm spiritual relation has a great impact on our belief system in facing difficult encounters in life. It helps every individual to have an assurance and to hold on unto someone who is powerful and can influence our actions towards well-driven goals.

Lesson Learned from the Teenage Mothers

There are many lessons that can be learned from the experiences of these young mothers. In real-life settings, challenges will always be associated in parenting most especially for adolescent parents who are obligated at an early age which is not supposed to be. These teenage mothers have their own shared difficulties that they faced during and after their pregnancy which can be a lesson for the readers. There are realizations and regrets that these young mothers wanted to share in order to convince and inform the teenage generation on how challenging their situation to be experienced in an inappropriate stage of life.

Advice for the teenagers concerning teenage pregnancy

Teenage parents have a bigger responsibility at an early age in an actual sense. Thus, it is a difficult road to experience and it is undeniable that those young mothers who managed the role of being a teenage parent for years are a reliable source of advice for the present generation of teenagers. Their learnings coming from their individual experience are a great guide as a basis for awareness and knowledge regarding teenage pregnancy.

(2) Perceptions and feelings towards teenage pregnancy

Experience is the best teacher, elaborating and unveiling the perception or thoughts and feelings of the young mothers in their pregnancy is significant to the society today. This will help us to know their stance and had gone throughout their pregnancy. Also, this will give awareness to the society about the phenomenon of teenage pregnancy in the country and to acknowledge the feelings of the young mothers. In this theme, we can also emphasize the resilience of the mothers when it comes to the reactions of those people who surround them.

Initial reaction of the young mother when they found out they were pregnant

Young mothers who are engaged early in pregnancy have almost the same reactions when they find out they are pregnant. For them, it is like a roller coaster of emotion. They were frightened or terrified, some of them were nervous and anxious but some of them were happy and excited about their pregnancy.

Reactions of their family/ Parents

Parents and family are the ones who should know the situation of their daughter. Most of the parents of the participants were angry and disappointed, some were sad and surprised, but they were also happy about the pregnancy of their daughters.

Reactions of their Friends/ classmates

The friends and classmates of the young mothers were surprised and happy after they found out about their pregnancy.

Reactions of their school/ community they belong to

In our society, teenage pregnancy is a big issue. The judgment and discrimination that the young mothers can get is much worse than the support they can get from other people. The reactions of the school and community where they belong is significant for us to know how society responds to the phenomenon of teenage pregnancy.

Perceptions in normalizing teenage pregnancy

It is important to know the thoughts or perceptions of the young mothers about normalizing teenage pregnancy, it is to give awareness to why and why not it should be done by the rest of the society.

(3) Meaningful goals

Knowing the meaningful goals of being a teen mother enables them to become a fundamental aspect for the development of their psychological resilience. It enables them to create meaningful and beneficial plans for their well-being and with their child.

Hindered goals on being a young mother

Every teenager has many dreams that he/she is eyeing to come true in the future. But when a girl makes herself engaged into early pregnancy, there is a high chance that her dreams and goals will be hindered and replaced by taking full responsibility to support her child.

Awareness of the society regarding the issues of young mothers

Teen mothers already experience every ounce of difficulty in taking full responsibility to their child. By providing awareness based on their experiences may unfold many positive or negative encounters of a teen mother.

(4) Barriers on achieving dreams and hope

Having a child is a new responsibility that every parent/s must face besides being a daughter. It is anticipated that teen mothers should provide the effort to support their child as well.

Events in life that need to be put on hold to give way for pregnancy

The moment a teenager engaged into early pregnancy, there will be instances that she would replace her duty and responsibility as a daughter to being a teen mother.

Regrets as a young mother

One aspect that was developed by young mothers are their doubts in life. Since teenage pregnancy is an unplanned event, most of the female adolescence was forced to align their decisions and plan in life into practical and wise life-time decisions that will support their child. Thus, teenage mothers who have regrets in their pregnancy can be a barrier to establish their psychological resilience.

(5) Sources of social support

Teenage mothers should be given social support for it plays an important role in improving and increasing adolescent resilience. It enables adolescent mothers to lay a solid foundation for overcoming the challenges of motherhood. This theme is composed of people and programs that really help the mothers to be more resilient and to overcome the adversities they encountered during and after they gave birth.

Support systems received during pregnancy

Support systems during pregnancy are important for the development of psychological resilience to young mothers. The six (6) participants had different support systems during their pregnancy and these were: Parents/family, partner, government programs, and friends.

Support systems received after they gave birth

Support systems after giving birth are as important as support systems during pregnancy. The support systems of most of the participants have changed. The six (6) participants received family/ parents support, partner's support and themselves.

Programs they benefited from as a teenage mother

The following programs really helped the young mothers to fill in their needs in their pregnancy. The programs mentioned by the participants were their support system they received from the society or the government. These are the 4Ps or the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program, their barangay health center and PhilHealth or the Philippine Health Insurance Corporation.

Awareness with regards to teenage pregnancy

As the young mothers talked about their experiences, they also mentioned the aspects that our society should be aware of about young mothers and may be the cause of the continual rising of teenage pregnancy in the country. They stated that lack of sex education, and the lack of program and opportunities for the young mothers are the concepts that we should be aware of.

Discussion and Recommendation

This section entails the discussion and recommendation of the study based on the data that was interpreted and categorized to incorporate the main themes of the research.

All of the themes and objectives presented in the study are reflected in the lived experiences and the development of Psychological Resilience among participants in their teenage pregnancy and early motherhood journeys. The first theme, *Experiences with family, partner, community, and school; and coping mechanisms* manifesting how teenage parents are significantly influenced by the people that surround them. Their struggles and support were almost affected by their environment most especially when it comes to social support and assistance they have received. This support can be sustained by the family, partner, community, and even through friends from the school where they are supposed to belong. It signifies the impact and value of these areas from the experiences of younger parents. They admitted that their situation will always fall into two outcomes, such circumstances will either be an acceptance coming from loved ones who will then lend their support right after or invalid disappointments and rejections coming from them. The data indicate that most teenage parents were experiencing a tantamount of stress and problems because of disappointments and regrets from the people around them and even at themselves which contributed to their psychological resilience through different coping strategies.

The second theme, *Perceptions and feelings towards teenage pregnancy* contains the unfolding thoughts and emotions of both the young mothers and the people around them. Anger, disappointment, and surprise were the common initial responses that emerged from the point of view of the family, friends and classmates, school and community of the mothers. On the other hand, frightened and terrified were the reactions of the young mothers when they found out they were pregnant. Despite this, these initial reactions eventually superseded by happiness, excitement and acceptance to both the mother and the people who surround them.

Teenage pregnancy has been a global issue for many years. Undeniably, teenagers nowadays encompass different mindset and perceptions about this issue. These young women who experienced teenage pregnancy themselves are not in favor of normalizing teenage pregnancy in any circumstances. They came to realize how difficult the life they chose. From being a mother to their child to sustenance of both of their needs and the balancing of being a student and a mother. In addition, engaging in teenage pregnancy only adds burdens to the parents and family. They are sometimes the ones who hold responsible for the needs of their daughter and granddaughter because of the lack of resources that the young mother has. There is nothing to justify this issue because financial stability will not ensure the well-being of the child as he or she grows. It requires emotional, physical, mental and financial preparedness and the right age to get pregnant to avoid health issues for both mother and child. Shifting from singleness to having a child is a big turn of events to a young mother. Everything can change and there are lots of responsibilities to be ready for.

Meaningful goals are the third theme of the study which depict how teenage mothers hone their dreams and goals in life. This encompasses their personal goals as a teenager only and their set of goals in order to support her child as a teen mother. The most crucial thing in becoming teen mothers are their personal goals that were replaced by taking full responsibility to support their child, specifically elaborating the negative impact to their future educational plans. It was absolutely set aside to put focus on giving welfare to their child. However, not all teenage mothers saw teenage pregnancy as a hindrance to continue achieving their personal goals in life, some of them even wholeheartedly accepted the fact that they will commit to a lifetime responsibility.

Another sub theme that was revealed is their goals on spreading awareness to the society about the ongoing issue of teenage mothers. Teenage years are commonly tasked to prioritize their education and work their way to pursue their personal dreams and goals. But when they make wrong decisions, specifically engaging in early pregnancy, that will trigger many difficulties and sacrifices that they need to face as consequences. Most of the young mothers often realize on the latter note how poverty created an impact on their experiences in pregnancy, alongside all the expenses needed to sustain their child. That is why adolescents should always be mindful of what they want to do in life, same as being responsible enough to face the consequences of their choices. Moreover, one thing that adolescents should be aware of is to prohibit normalizing teenage pregnancy which should not be supported in the first place prior to its lifetime commitment and responsibility of the teenage parents pertaining to their child. During this time, issues about engaging in teenage pregnancy are becoming a new trend that many adolescents overlook the major effect of the phenomenon not only to their life but also to the society as well. Which is why addressing the issue about the insufficient education on sexual and reproductive health can promote better understanding to the mentioned context.

The fourth theme, *Barriers on achieving dreams and hope* explained how teenage pregnancy creates a significant effect on their lifetime. Teenagers will be forced to leave the adolescent period and change it to more mature actions and decisions that will enable them to support their child, instances where they will quit their education to seek a job at an early age. The sub themes that were revealed in the study pertaining to the events that need to be put on hold to give way for pregnancy are their personal goals such as their hobbies in going out with their friends and putting away their wants as an adolescent in order for them to take care of their child.

Engaging in early pregnancy was the common regret a young mother realizes as time goes by. The activity led teenage mothers to feel disappointed with themselves and from their parents as well since they had to set aside their future dreams and goals in order to sustain the needs and wants of their child.

The fifth and final theme is the *Sources of Social Support*. Support systems or social support really helped to overcome the challenges that the young mothers faced and currently experiencing. Family, partners, friends, and government programs really helped the teenage mothers to surpass the challenges of pregnancy. Pregnancy is one of the critical phases of becoming a mother especially when they got pregnant at such a young age. There are lots of risk factors that may arise if the needs of the mothers are not supplemented adequately. It may harm both the mother and their child. Fortunately, these young mothers received adequate prenatal care from their support systems.

The real challenge begins when the child is born and growing. The level of needs is also upgrading, from diapers, milk and vitamins to regular checkups and vaccines. These young mothers found support financially and emotionally from their family and parents, partners and themselves. Time management is a big challenge for them particularly for the young mothers who chose to continue their studies. Some of them experienced psychological distress and mostly lack of sleep but with the help of their support systems after giving birth, they got a grip on themselves.

Government supports such as 4Ps, PhilHealth, and health centers lessen the burden of financial distress from hospital bills and filling in the necessities of some young mothers. In contrast, most of them don't receive anything from the government, specifically, from their barangay, for the reason that they chose to attend private clinics to ensure the privacy of their pregnancy. Overall, health care centers and government based programs will be really helpful to everyone not just for mothers if we have access to them.

The opinions and perceptions of teenage mothers are important for the betterment of the programs intended for them and enhancement of the prevention of the said phenomenon. Teenage mothers saw proper sex education, knowledge in using contraceptives and lacks of programs and opportunities for young mothers as the insufficient aspects that needs to be addressed by the society. Due to the conservative nature of the Philippines, most people are still awkward when they talk about sex. Even some teachers who taught about this are avoiding this topic, and sometimes instead of using the proper and real names of the parts of the reproductive systems, they tend to overshadow it with flowery terms. Furthermore, the lack of knowledge about sex education leads to the curiosity of the teenagers to grow, which will eventually lead to practicing unsafe sex and misuse of contraceptives. On another note, lack of programs and job opportunities is what young mothers want the government to pay attention to. This may give them fair opportunities to learn and provide help for their family.

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